

Implementing an ensemble classifier based on a trainable combiner for liver disease diagnosis

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Abstract

The liver is the largest gland in the body that plays a role in digestive activities such as digestion. The entire gastrointestinal tract is collected by encephalitis called portal vein and enters the liver, and all the absorbed material from the gastrointestinal tract passes through the liver. Other liver tasks are trapping toxins and treating them by turning them into harmless substances. Also, this liver is responsible for the metabolism of drugs in the body. Participating in prenatal hemorrhage and resistance to infections, providing rapid energy when needed, storing iron, and other liver functions. The liver cells permanently make various proteins, including albumin, prothrombin, fibrinogen, lipoproteins and heparin. The liver acts as an important buffering system for blood glucose, which means that when glucose levels increase after a single meal to a high concentration, insulin secretion also increases and about 60% of the glucose absorbed from the intestine immediately into glycogen Converted and stored in the liver Machine learning is used in medical diagnostics and has achieved very good results. We used an advanced model to diagnose liver disease in this thesis. The proposed model in this thesis is made up of a seven-class combination. The innovation of this proposed method is in their combination. We use a class to combine seven classes and provide the final answer. In the second chapter, we reviewed the articles presented with the topic of diagnosis of liver disease using artificial intelligence-based methods. By analyzing the articles, we concluded that the combination methods yielded more reliable results. In this thesis, a trained combinatory is used to combine seven grades. According to the last part of the third chapter, we created the new data set. By analyzing the results, we concluded that the combined method of the seven-class stratified individually had a dramatic improvement in efficiency. The result of the proposed combination method is 87/1.

Keywords: Liver Disease, Data mining, Classification, Classification Combinations, Educational Combination

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References

- [1] S. H. Caldwell et al., "Coagulation disorders and hemostasis in liver disease: pathophysiology and critical assessment of current management," *Hepatology*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 1039–1046, 2006.
- [2] "25 Ways to Love Your Liver Health," American Liver Foundation, 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.liverfoundation.org/abouttheliver/25ways>. [Accessed: 14-Jan-2015].
- [3] M. Lundin, J. Lundin, H. B. Burke, S. Toikkanen, and L. Pylkkänen, "Artificial Neural Networks Applied to Survival Prediction in Breast Cancer," *Oncology*, vol. 57, pp. 281–286, 1999.
- [4] M. Nazaridoust and B. Bidgoli, "Data Mining of Associate Degree Accepted Candidates by," *Proceeding 2nd World Conf. Soft Comput.*, pp. 558–563, 2009.
- [5] B. Venkata Ramana, M. S. P. Babu, and N. . Venkateswarlu, "A Critical Study of Selected Classification Algorithms for Liver Disease Diagnosis," *Int. J. Database Manag. Syst.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 101–114, 2011.
- [6] P. M. Surendra and P. Babu, "New Automatic Diagnosis of Liver Status Using Bayesian Classification," no. *Icinc*, pp. 385–388, 2010.
- [7] P. Domingos and M. Pazzani, "On the Optimality of the Simple Bayesian Classifier under Zero-One Los," *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 103–130, 1997.
- [8] C.-H. Weng, T. C.-K. Huang, and R.-P. Han, "Disease prediction with different types of neural network classifiers," *Telemat. Informatics*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 277–292, 2016.
- [9] J. Pahareeya, "Liver Patient Classification using Intelligence Techniques," vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 295–299, 2014.
- [10] B. Venkata Ramana, M. Surendra Prasad Babu, and N. B. Venkateswarlu, "A Critical Comparative Study of Liver Patients from USA and INDIA: An Exploratory Analysis," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Issues*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 506–516, 2012.
- [11] M. Abdar, M. Zomorodi-Moghadam, R. Das, and I. H. Ting, "Performance analysis of classification algorithms on early detection of liver disease," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 67, pp. 239–251, 2017.
- [12] E. M. F. El Houby, "A survey on applying machine learning techniques for management of diseases," *J. Appl. Biomed.*, no. 2017, 2018.
- [13] H.-H. Rau et al., "Development of a web-based liver cancer prediction model for type II diabetes patients by using an artificial neural network," *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.*, vol. 125, pp. 58–65, 2016.
- [14] C. J. Tseng, C. J. Lu, C. C. Chang, G. Den Chen, and C. Cheewakriangkrai, "Integration of data mining classification techniques and ensemble learning to identify risk factors and diagnose ovarian cancer recurrence," *Artif. Intell. Med.*, vol. 78, pp. 47–54, 2017.
- [15] X. Yang et al., "Segmentation of liver and vessels from CT images and classification of liver segments for preoperative liver surgical planning in living donor liver transplantation," *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.*, vol. 158, pp. 41–52, 2018.
A. P. Toropova and A. A. Toropov, "CORAL: Binary classifications (active/inactive) for drug-induced liver injury," *Toxicol. Lett.*, vol. 268, pp. 51–57, 2017.
- [16] X. Zhu and N. L. Kruhlak, "Construction and analysis of a human hepatotoxicity database suitable for QSAR modeling using post-market safety data," *Toxicology*, vol. 321, no. 1, pp. 62–72, 2014.

- A. Naik and L. Samant, "Correlation Review of Classification Algorithm Using Data Mining Tool: WEKA, Rapidminer, Tanagra, Orange and Knime," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 85, no. Cms, pp. 662–668, 2016.
- [17] Gulia, R. Vohra, and P. Rani, "Liver patient classification using intelligent techniques," *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Inf. Technol.*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 5110–5115, 2014.
- [18] T. Yau, V. Y. F. Tang, T. J. Yao, S. T. Fan, C. M. Lo, and R. T. P. Poon, "Development of Hong Kong liver cancer staging system with treatment stratification for patients with hepatocellular carcinoma," *Gastroenterology*, vol. 146, no. 7, p. 1691–1700.e3, 2014.
- [19] M. S. D. Dr. S. Vijayarani, "Liver Disease Prediction using SVM and Naïve Bayes Algorithms," *Int. J. Sci. Eng. Technol. Res.*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 816–820, 2015.
- [20] J. M. Tomczak and M. Zięba, "Probabilistic combination of classification rules and its application to medical diagnosis," *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 101, no. 1–3, pp. 105–135, 2015.
- [21] J. M. RodrÃ-guez-JimÃ©nez, P. Cordero, M. Enciso, and A. Mora, "Data mining algorithms to compute mixed concepts with negative attributes: an application to breast cancer data analysis," *Math. Methods Appl. Sci.*, vol. 39, no. 16, pp. 4829–4845, 2016.
- [22] H. Jin, S. Kim, and J. Kim, "Decision factors on effective liver patient data prediction," *Int. J. Bio-Science Bio-Technology*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 167–178, 2014.
- [23] S. Bahramirad, A. Mustapha, and M. Eshraghi, "Classification of liver disease diagnosis: a comparative study," in *Informatics and applications (ICIA), 2013 second international conference on*, 2013, pp. 42–46.
- [24] E. M. Hashem and M. S. Mabrouk, "A Study of Support Vector Machine Algorithm for Liver Disease Diagnosis," *Am. J. Intell. Syst.*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 9–14, 2014.
- [25] Liang and L. Peng, "An Automated Diagnosis System of Liver Disease using Artificial Immune and Genetic Algorithms," *J. Med. Syst.*, vol. 37, no. 2, p. 9932, Apr. 2013.
- [26] S. Kant and I. A. Ansari, "An improved K means clustering with Atkinson index to classify liver patient dataset," *Int. J. Syst. Assur. Eng. Manag.*, vol. 7, no. S1, pp. 222–228, Dec. 2016.
- [27] V. Ramana, P. M. Surendra, and P. Babu, "Liver Classification Using Modified Rotation Forest," vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 17–24, 2012.
- [28] H. Ratnamala Kiruba and G. Tholkappia Arasu, "An intelligent Agent based framework for liver disorder diagnosis using artificial intelligence techniques," *J. Theor. Appl. Inf. Technol.*, vol. 69, no. 1, pp. 91–100, 2014.
- A. S. Aneeshkumar and Cj. J. Venkateswaran, "Estimating the surveillance of liver disorder using classification algorithms," *Int. J. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 57, no. 6, pp. 975–8887, 2012.
- [29] S. Karthik, a Priyadarishini, J. Anuradha, and B. K. Tripathy, "Classification and Rule Extraction using Rough Set for Diagnosis of Liver Disease and its Types," *Liver*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 334–345, 2011.
- [30] P. A. Jaskowiak and R. J. G. B. Campello, "Comparing Correlation Coefficients as Dissimilarity Measures for Cancer Classification in Gene Expression Data." 2011.
- [31] Coomans and D. L. Massart, "Alternative k-nearest neighbour rules in supervised pattern recognition," *Anal. Chim. Acta*, vol. 136, pp. 15–27, 1982.
- [32] Nigsch, A. Bender, B. van Buuren, J. Tissen, E. Nigsch, and J. B. O. Mitchell, "Melting Point Prediction Employing k-Nearest Neighbor Algorithms and Genetic

- Parameter Optimization,” J. Chem. Inf. Model., vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 2412–2422, Nov. 2006.
- [33] P. Hall, B. U. Park, and R. J. Samworth, “Choice of neighbor order in nearest-neighbor classification,” *Ann. Stat.*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 2135–2152, Oct. 2008.
- [34] Rosenblatt, *The perceptron, a perceiving and recognizing automaton Project Para.* Cornell Aeronautical Laboratory, 1957.
- [35] M. Olazaran, “A Sociological Study of the Official History of the Perceptrons Controversy,” *Soc. Stud. Sci.*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 611–659, Aug. 1996.
- [36] J. R. Quinlan, “Simplifying Decision Trees,” *Int. J. Man-Mach. Stud.*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 221–234, Sep. 1987.
- [37] J. S.K. and S. S., “Reptree Classifier for Identifying Link Spam in Web Search Engines,” *ICTACT J. Soft Comput.*, vol. 03, no. 02, pp. 498–505, 2013.
- [38] R. C. Holte, “Very Simple Classification Rules Perform Well on Most Commonly Used Datasets,” *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 63–91, 1993.
- [39] R. C. Holte, L. Acker, and B. Porter, “Concept Learning and the Problem of Small Disjuncts,” *Ijcai*, pp. 813–818, 1989.
- [40] Azgomi, H., & Mahjur, A. (2013). *A Solution for Calculating the False Positive and False Negative in LSH Method to Find Similar Documents*. *Journal of Basic and Applied Research*, 3(1s), 466-472.
- [41] Azgomi, H. (2013). *Finding similar documents by removing redundant characters*. (master dissertation). Islamic Azad University of Shabestar, Shabestar, Iran.
- [42] Azgomi, H., Ghasemi Mahsayeh, M., & Mohammadpour, M. (2013). *A Method for Finding Similar Documents Based on Selection a Range for Substring Lenght in Shingling Method*. *Reef Resources Assessment and Management Technical Paper*, 38(5).
- [43] Azgomi, H., Ghasemi Mahsayeh, M., Mohammadi, M., & Moradi, M. (2014). *A Method for Finding Similar Documents Relying on Adding Repetition of Symbols in Length Based Filtering*. *Indian Journal of Scientific Research*, 2(1), 81-84.
- [44] Azgomi, H., & Ghasemi Mahsayeh, M (2014). *Finding Similar Items In Data mining: Shingling Method*, Presentation, Iran.
- [45] Azgomi, H., & Ghasemi Mahsayeh, Ma. (2013). *Finding Similar Documents by Repetition of Symbols in Length Based Filtering*. *International Conference on Computer, Information Technology and Digital Media*, Tehran, Iran.
- [46] Azgomi, H. (2015). *Apriori Source Code in VB, Java and C#*.
- [47] Ghasemi Mahsayeh, M., & Mahjur, A. (2013). *A Method for Finding Similar Documents on the Basis of Repetition-Based Filtering*. *Journal of Basic and Applied Research*, 3(1s), 603-607.
- [48] Ghasemi Mahsayeh, M. (2013). *Finding similar documents relying on repetition based filtering*. (master dissertation). Islamic Azad University of Shabestar, Shabestar, Iran.
- [49] Sohrabi, M. K., & Azgomi, H. (2017). TSGV: a table-like structure-based greedy method for materialized view selection in data warehouses. *Turkish Journal of Electrical Engineering & Computer Sciences*, 25(4), 3175-3187.
- [50] Sohrabi, M. K., & Azgomi, H. (2017). Parallel set similarity join on big data based on Locality-Sensitive Hashing. *Science of Computer Programming*, 145, 1-12.
- [51] Azgomi, H., & Sohrabi, M. K. (2018). A game theory based framework for materialized view selection in data warehouses. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 71, 125-137.

- [52] Azgomi, H., & Sohrabi, M. K. (2018). Finding *similar documents using frequent pattern mining methods*. International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems.
- [53] Azgomi, H. (2018). Thesis: *A game theory based framework for materialized view selection in data warehouse*. (Doctoral dissertation). Islamic Azad University of Semnan, Semnan, Iran. 10.13140/RG.2.2.20178.45766.
- [54] Azgomi, H., & Sohrabi, M. K. (2017). *RTLTDs Dataset*. 10.13140/RG.2.2.35186.81608.
- [55] Azgomi, H. (2017). *RTLTDs Data Warehouse*. 10.13140/RG.2.2.35513.88166.
- [56] Sohrabi, M. K., & Azgomi, H. (2018). Evolutionary game theory approach to materialized view selection in data warehouses. *Knowledge-Based Systems*.
- [57] Sohrabi, M. K., & Azgomi, H. A Survey on the Combined Use of Optimization Methods and Game Theory. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, 1-22.